

Corona Epidemic and the Evaluation of University instructors Academic Productions College of Education–Ibn Rushd as a Sample 2019-2022

Muhammad AmerJamil, Sabah Mahdi Rumayd

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 04 , 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Pandemic, Academic production, Instructors, College of Education/ Ibn Rushd</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6792751</p>	<p><i>The study aims at identifying the Iraqi university instructors' academic production (at the College of Education/IbnRushd) in terms of their own perspectives and to recognize the differences among their responses in terms of gender, academic achievements, corona positive or negative infection, years of experience, academic titles and years of age.</i></p> <p><i>To verify the hypotheses and to achieve this aim, the researchers have applied the analytical descriptive approach and have designed the research instrument which comprises (18) items. Then, they have proved its validity and reliability by getting the educationists' approval.</i></p> <p><i>The collected data has been analysed by calculating the arithmetic means and standard deviations. The results show that the hypothetical means are larger than the arithmetic means in terms of statistical significance in favor to the hypothetical means.</i></p> <p><i>It is concluded that the sample of this study has less academic production than hypothetically expected. Accordingly, the researchers call for the necessity to advise the university staff to follow the individual and social health protection procedures and take the vaccine in order to keep himself and others safe.</i></p>

Introduction

The problem of the study started from the exacerbation of the health and psychological concerns of individuals with the outbreak of the Corona pandemic and its serious repercussions on the whole world, especially that the Corona virus has the super ability to transform and renew up to America. Which raised the alarm once again, in addition to the aggravation of economic difficulties and the attendant serious repercussions that affected the standard of living for all segments of society, and there is no doubt that the education sector is part of it, as the level of scientific production of Iraqi university professors (the study model) was affected by the professors of the Faculty of Education IbnRushd, University of Baghdad, especially those infected with the virus. This was reflected in the level of their scientific outputs compared to their healthy colleagues.

There is also no doubt that the quality of the educational system depends entirely on the performance level of the university professor, the achievement of scientific research through written and translated books, published articles, participation in local and international specialized scientific conferences, as well as teaching. activities, so the reform of any society depends on the reform of performance. However, what was observed during the outbreak of the Corona Covid 19 pandemic, there is a clear decline in the productivity of faculty members in the fields of authorship, research and translation, and performance remains restricted in the e-learning process as an alternative measure for personal education, and there is no doubt that this is a dangerous indicator, It contributed to Iraq's exit from the world rankings, according to the report issued by the World Economic Forum. Davos Forum (*), which excluded Iraq and some Arab countries for their lack of quality standards at the level of higher, secondary and primary education, as well as in the Shanghai and Tong Academic Ranking of Universities (ranking universities). Kalima Universities Academy, 2003) which adopted accurate standards, including (quality of education, quality of faculty members). Q, and the quality of research performance), as measured by the index of the number of articles published in refereed scientific journals within international capacities such as nature and science, research recorded in the social science indexes, and the index of preparing articles in the special citations index. The social sciences as well as the standard of academic performance against the size of the university. (Shahin, SherifKamel, 2013: 56), as well as what was referred to by the World Declaration on Higher Education in the Twenty-first Century issued by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 1998). Its tenth article states that

The necessity of adopting strict policies towards university professors and taking the necessary measures to enable them to conduct research, improves their skills, and motivates them for sustainable innovation, especially in the field of scientific research. There is no doubt that these centers work through full-time researchers for this (The Third Arab Development and Culture Report, 2010: 59), hence the idea of the study with the aim of identifying the level of repercussions. The Corona pandemic is affecting the productivity of university

professors. The researchers identified the IbnRushd College of Education at the University of Baghdad as a model during the period (2019). / 2022)

The Importance Of Studying

The importance of the study was determined in that it identified the dangerous indicators and difficult challenges created by the Corona pandemic, especially on higher education institutions in Iraq, foremost of which is the level of scientific productivity of university professors, who are the main active component. In the sustainability of scientific interaction and communication at the regional and international levels.

There is no doubt that higher education institutions are among the most important stages of education that work on preparing qualified academic cadres to lead community institutions and a basic pillar for the development of a productive society, in addition to investing in knowledge capital to achieve it. Advancing and achieving its goals and objectives (Al-Tal 1997: 105). Therefore, the new problems facing university policy in our time are the explosion of knowledge, as predictions indicate the volume of information that may discover in the next twenty years the need for individuals with expertise in the fields of research and investigation, as well as their ability to confront these problems, which means that we are in there is an urgent need for thinking professors who are able to provide societies with scientific products, especially in light of cognitive and other variables (Andrea, 1994: 1), then work to overcome all the difficulties of the stage and the effects of this epidemic, and then work on the quality of higher education outputs through the achieved steps a well-thought-out mission whose mission is to improve academic research and the quality of academic supervision, and what that constitutes essential elements in university life, and then leads to immunizing individuals with the assets of knowledge and advanced research methods.

(*The World Economic Forum Davos is an independent, international, not-for-profit organization charged with developing the world by encouraging business, politics, science and all community leaders to shape the global, regional and economic agenda.

(Schafer, 2000, p: 8) globally, and therefore higher education institutions of the world fulfill the task of contributing in one way or another to the development of their human resources with the academic qualifications they possess that enable them to drive the wheel. Development University professors are the component, hence the example of the scientific outputs of university professors as a main entrance to achieve what is expected of them, as what the university offers to members of its community and the development of their environments is linked to the extent of their spread. Master their research tasks in addition to their main teaching tasks (Al-Hadith, 2006:389) either in person or electronically.

The importance of the study and its data

The significance and data of the study were determined in the context of the following matters:

1. The importance of the study lies in the exacerbation of the Corona pandemic and its serious repercussions on the entire public life, including university professors who constitute an important segment and the nucleus of life development and sustainability.
2. The study focuses on how to invest human resources, especially Iraqi university professors, as the best investment in order to obtain effective positive results that serve the issues of society and develop solutions to its contemporary problems.
3. The study variable occupied the center stage in contemporary studies despite passing through several problems, but the visions and orientations of thinkers and researchers in various fields facilitated the difficulties facing the stage.
4. The importance of the study appears through the results of the level of scientific outputs in Iraqi universities in an attempt to alert decision makers to develop strategies and mechanisms that facilitate the efforts of researchers and motivate them to continue scientific production. In terms of quantity and quality, especially under exceptional circumstances such as the outbreak of the Corona Covid-19 epidemic.
5. Enhancing the self-capacities of university professors and overcoming the psychological conditions, especially for professors infected with this epidemic and those recovering from it.

Objectives of the study

The study requires disclosure of the following- :

- Limits of the level of scientific outputs of Iraqi university professors in the College of Education - IbnRushd from their point of view.
- The differences between the responses of the study sample members (the professors of the College of Education IbnRushd) are due to the variables (gender (teaching - teaching), academic achievement, members of the teaching staff infected with the epidemic and those not infected., the number of years of service, scientific titles, as well as the age groups of teachers)

The limits of the study

The geographical location of the study was determined for the professors of the College of Education IbnRushd, University of Baghdad / Republic of Iraq for the academic year 2021/2022.

Concepts and terms included in the study:

The study called for defining the concept of scientific production, including its theoretical and procedural concepts.

- Scientific outputs: the sum of the scientific works and activities of university professors distributed on scientific research published and accepted for publication in academic scientific journals, written and translated books, and working papers presented at scientific conferences, educational seminars and university scientific supervision. Theses and dissertations as well as activities in institutions and NGOs. (Alshaya, 2006:30)
- Theoretical concept: There are two directions in the interpretation of the concept: the first is qualitative quantitative production, and the second is the cumulative scientific production represented by the number of books authored and scientific research published during a specified period of time, consideration. productivity index level.
- Procedural concept: the total score that the respondent (the target group) will obtain by answering the paragraphs of the questionnaire prepared for this purpose.

Theoretical framework background

The boundaries of higher education institutions and their development path are among the most important factors of comprehensive development, as they represent the basic factor for any human development due to the reliable knowledge frameworks that they provide in the areas of development and change. Community service, which is why it is required more than ever to advance its capabilities and levels in order to be able to perform its duties to the fullest, and this is not achieved by weakness or lack of scientific outputs for those in the university corps. (Al-Rubaie 23: 2008)

Educational studies showed its interest in the subject of productivity and dealing with its various environments, including the study of motion and time by Taylor, and then followed by the Hawthorn experiments carried out by Eaton Mayo, which aimed to discover the best way to raise the level of productivity in industrial and educational institutions, as it showed the impact of the human factor in Determining the level of productivity according to customs. It was approved by the non-governmental working group, and pointed out the importance of moral incentives in raising the level of individual and organizational productivity. (Robbins, 1990: p34)

The last three decades of the twentieth century witnessed more interest in scientific productivity as it aims to develop a society that is achieved through two means, the first by adding new capital assets, and the second by improving performance and raising productivity rates for all units (Hamami and Khalaf, 1994: 285)

This is what United Bavendam Research Company explained in 1999 that the study of productivity is important for all institutions, whether they are service or manufacturing, and even non-profit institutions seek to do a lot by reducing the pace of productivity, according to what Deming indicated, most of the productivity of the institution is affected by the productivity process. . The realism itself, the devices you use and the way you handle the materials, as well as the number of errors resulting from the performance of the system followed and the work-flow models, all lead to a comprehensive confusion in the production efficiency of the enterprise and the occurrence of deficiencies in it. (Deming, 1999: pp. 1-2)

When comparing the education sector with other sectors, we note that there is an agreement to produce a service related to the goals of the educational system, and one of the education outputs is the expansion of the Knowledge and Human Sciences Authority. Among individuals, another product is measured by the development of civilization, and a product like it is measured by the expansion of the stock of human resources. (Hallaq, 1996: p. 14), and in light of what has been shown, the factors affecting the improvement of the level of scientific productivity can be explained as contained in (Al-Atiyah, 1982: 120) and as follows:

1. Determining goals and priorities in a planned timetable and employing them in the field of scientific research and other auxiliary activities.
2. Sustainability of following up on the obstacle of aspects of scientific productivity to diagnose it and then develop solutions to address it.
3. Effective linking between performance and mutual expectations between departments of university institutions and between incentives, communication and communication systems.
4. Urging researchers to collective and organizational creativity and to produce what serves the requirements of contemporary society and twinning between Arab and international universities.
5. Develop clear procedural concepts and qualitative standards that help in understanding scientific productivity in universities and within an applied framework.
6. Allocating a financial budget for the purpose of conducting applied scientific research, with allocating rewards for the best research completed and published in international refereed journals, preferably with an estimate of global containers annually.

Problems that limit the scientific productivity of university professors from the perspective of previous studies. Several studies differed in identifying the problems that contributed to the classification of weak scientific productivity among university professors, including the following:

First: Study (Hassan Pasha, 1983 AD) King Saud University in Riyadh

1. Concerning the privacy of the faculty member.

2. What is related to the performance of the university?
3. Concerning the local community.

Second: Study (Ibrahim Haddad 1990) Arab Republic of Egypt.

1. Lack of social appreciation for research and researchers.
2. Lack of appropriate training to prepare Arab researchers.
3. Lack of suitable environment for scientific research and production.
4. Weakness of scientific and technological capabilities in the environment of researchers.
5. Weak spirit of cooperation and competition among researchers, especially in the field of scientific research.

Third: Study (SalamaTanash, 1992) the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

1. Weak enough financial funds to support researchers in conducting scientific research.
2. Many professors are preoccupied with the teaching process and other accompanying activities that prevent them from allowing enough time to write scientific research and activate its applications.
3. The limited activities of sending professors abroad to benefit from the fields of scientific research in countries that depend on basic scientific research in preparing their scientific curricula.

Fourth: (Study of Muhammad Abdul-Dirani, 1997) University of Jordan / Jordan.

1. Delaying and obstructing the publication of research in refereed scientific journals.

Fifth: Study (ZakiHannoush 1997) University of Aleppo / Syria.

1. Doubling the expenses of scientific research and the budget allocated to it.
2. Concerning the work mechanism, periodicals, teaching loads, communication systems, administrative work routine, rewards and incentives.
3. The weak motivation of most faculty members to conduct scientific research due to the lack of interest in some university institutions.

Sixth: A study (AfafShukri 1998) on the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

1. Weak communication and cooperation between researchers within the same country or between them and Arab countries, especially in the field of information and cross-fertilization of scientific ideas and plans.

Seventh: Study (Matanios Michael 1999) Lebanon.

1. Insufficient financial resources allocated to the field of scientific research writing.
2. Lack of research frameworks.
3. Low levels of some professors.
4. Migration of scientific competencies to developed countries as a result of the economic and political conditions within their countries.
5. Lack of research facilities needed for researchers.
6. Poor communication between research producers and consumers.
7. Administrative difficulties and their implications for the productive motivation of researchers.

Eighth: Study (Ahmed Kanaan 2001) the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

1. Weak cooperation between universities and research beneficiaries.
2. The lack of sufficient financial transfers to support scientific research.
3. Lack of references and modern sources and their use in the field of scientific research.
4. The absence of a central plan in the field of writing scientific research at the level of universities and colleges.
5. Weak cooperation of colleagues in conducting joint research.
6. Lack of teacher hours, which turns the trend towards the practical production path.
7. Not preparing delegates to developed countries to keep pace with scientific research.
8. The lack of an appropriate scientific climate for conducting scientific research, especially applied research.

As for the current study, it added to the problems that were addressed in the context of the above studies, the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic and its repercussions on the mechanism of scientific outputs for university professors, at a time when university institutions should be the pioneers in the field of employing the product of university operations and products in community service, as well as providing Other services according to a systematic plan compatible with the strategic plans of the state administration, taking into account the challenges of the current stage.

Study methodology and procedures

The study identified its population, sample and methodology, in addition to preparing the study tool, its procedural steps, and the statistical methods used in it, as follows:

Study Approach

In order to reach the study's objectives and hypotheses, the descriptive approach associated with the analytical method was used, relying on events and phenomena that exist in reality and are measurable as they are without

the intervention of researchers in the course of their occurrence. Thus, this approach is considered the closest in the field of educational and psychological studies research.

First: the study community

The study population was determined by the faculty members at IbnRushd College of Education for Human Sciences, University of Baghdad, and their number was (252) * male and female teachers, (114) male teachers, and (138) female teachers for the academic year 2021/2022, as shown in Table No. (1)

Table (1) Distribution of the study population and their proportions

Gender	Number	Percentage %
Lecturer - Lecturer		
Lecturer male	114	46
Lecturer female	138	54
Total	252	100

Second: the study sample

The study sample was chosen by the random class, which numbered (100) teachers, with (55) male and (45) female teachers, ie (40%) as shown in Tables (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7) to show the distribution of the study sample members according to their variables and percentages, as shown in the data in the tables below.

Table (2) Distribution of study sample members according to gender variable and their ratios

Gender	Number	Percentage %
Lecturer - Lecturer		
Lecturer Male	55	55
Lecturer Female	45	45
Total	100	100

Table (3) Distribution of study sample members according to academic achievement variable and their percentages

Academic achievement	Number	Percentage %
Master's	8	8
PhD	92	92
Total	100	100

The two researchers obtained the required statistical information about the professors of the Faculty of Education IbnRushd (the study sample) for the academic year 2021/2022 through the website of the mentioned college, see the website <http://www.ircoedu.uobaghdad.edu.ig//>.

Table (4) Distribution of the study sample members of professors infected with the virus and those who were not infected, and their percentages

Education Institution	Lecturer Male	Lecturer Female	Total	Percentage %
The number of people infected with the virus	39	45	84	84
The number of people who have not been infected with the virus	16	0	16	16
Total	55	45	100	100

Table (5) Distribution of study sample members according to years of service and their percentage

Years of service	Number	Percentage %
5 years	7	7
5-10 years	22	22
10-20 years	40	40
20 and more	31	31
Total	100	100

Table (6) Distribution of study sample members according to scientific names and their lineage

Scientific titles	Lecturer male	Lecturer female	Total	Percentage %
Prof. Dr.	27	15	42	42
Assistant Prof. Dr.	20	22	42	42
Dr.	7	6	13	13

Assistant Lecturer	1	2	4	4
Total	55	45	100	100

Table (7) Distribution of study sample members according to the variable age of the faculty and their percentages

Faculty age groups	Number	Percentage %
Thirties	14	14
Forties	53	53
Fifties	33	33
Total	100	100

Third: the study tool

The questionnaire was used as a tool for the study, as it is one of the most appropriate tools for obtaining information and data used in preparing the current study, and for the purpose of building the study tool (the questionnaire) the following procedural steps were taken:

1. Examining educational data and previous studies related to the topic and their usefulness in how to develop the basics of the tool and knowing how to formulate paragraphs and the limits of their use.
2. Employing and enhancing the expertise of researchers in the educational field in formulating the questionnaire's paragraphs.
3. Holding meetings with a group of professors specialized in the field of educational and psychological sciences and conducting dialogues with them about the formation of the questionnaire's paragraphs.

After completing the formulation of the questionnaire which has been completed in two parts:

The first part: General information about the professors of the IbnRushd College of Education for the Humanities (the target group) represented in (teaching and teaching sex, academic achievement, members of the teaching staff infected with the epidemic and those who are not infected, and their number). years of service, academic titles, as well as the age groups of teachers)

The second part: - The study tool (the questionnaire) included (18) paragraphs that were sent electronically to the target sample and they were answered.

Psychometric properties of the study instrument

In order for the study tool to be effective in measuring the phenomenon, it must be characterized by some psychometric properties, including the following: - (Ebel, 1972: p432)

A- Apparent honesty

Honesty is one of the most important normative characteristics that must be available in educational and psychological standards, and it is intended to measure the characteristic that has been described in order to be measured. (Al-Naama and Al-Ajili, 2014: 241), and therefore the researchers relied on apparent honesty by presenting the study tool to a group of arbitrators (*) specialized in educational and psychological sciences to ensure the adequacy of the study tool (the questionnaire) in terms of paragraphs and the diversity of its content and assessing the level of drafting and output rules Grammatically accurate.

B- Tool stability

The stability of the instrument is one of the conditions that must be met in educational and psychological tests and standards, as it means that the instrument is characterized by stability and stability in what it measures. It includes dividing the tool into two parts, each containing the same paragraphs or more than one paragraph from the other, then finding the correlation coefficient between the two parts, then making a statistical correction and adjusting the correlation coefficient using Spearman - the structured predictive equation, and accordingly the reliability coefficient for the whole tool was (0, 77), which is a reliable coefficient of good stability. With this procedure, the tool is ready for application.

(*)The names and scientific presentations of the arbitrators in this study

T Scientific title Triple name Major Place of work

1. Prof. Dr. SobeihKaramZamil, Educational Administration, University College of Peace
2. Prof. Alaa Hakim Nasser, Educational Administration, College of Education, Ibn Al-Haytham
3. Prof. Osama Hamid Hassan measuring and evaluating the Open Educational College
4. Prof. Dr. M. Sadiq Abdel Aziz Nour Measuring and evaluating the Open Educational College
5. Prof. Dr. Mohsen Saleh Hassan, Educational Psychology, Iraqi University / College of Arts

Fourth: Statistical means

For the purpose of processing the study data, the statistical package (SPSS) was used to analyze the data, which are as follows:-

- Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and percentages.
- The T-test of a sample drawn from a known population.
- T-test for two independent samples.
- One-way analysis of variance.

- Schaffer multiple comparisons test.
- Spearman's correlation coefficient to find stability by the split-half method.

Presentation and interpretation of results

Determine the objective of the study (statement of assessing the level of the Corona pandemic covid19 on the scientific productivity of the professors of the IbnRushd College of Education for the academic year 2019-2022) To verify the goal, it is necessary to identify the statistical differences between the average scores of the sample (Professors of the College of Education IbnRushd for Human Sciences) and the hypothetical average of the scientific outcomes tool at the level of significance (0.05) and Table (8) illustrates this.

Table (8) It shows the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the scientific results scores and the calculated t value

Study tool	Number of paragraphs	Average arithmetic	Standard deviation	Hypothetical mean	Degree of freedom	Calculated t value	T-Table Value	Statistical Significance Level (0.05)
Scientific outputs	18	20,05	11,05	36	99	14,02	1,96	A function in favor of the hypothetical mean

The arithmetic mean was extracted for a sample of 100 male and female teachers, and it was found that the arithmetic mean was (20.05) and the standard deviation was (11.05), while the default mean of the tool (36), and it is noted that the default mean is much greater than the mean Arithmetic. If the difference was statistically significant, then the t-test was used for a sample taken from a known population, and it appeared that the calculated t-value (14.02) was greater than the tabular value (1.96) and with a degree of freedom (99) at the significance level (0, 05), which means That the observed difference is statistically significant, and since the arithmetic mean is smaller than the default mean of the tool, the difference is in favor of the default mean, and this is an indication that the study sample showed low scientific production, especially during the outbreak of the Covid 19 pandemic. This result agrees in addition To the problems classified in previous studies with (Hassan Pasha study 1983, Ibrahim Haddad study 1990, Michael 1999 study, Ahmed Kanaan study 2001), and to verify the main objective, the following hypotheses must be answered:

The first hypothesis (there are no significant differences at the significance level (0.05) between the arithmetic mean and the hypothetical mean by gender (education and teaching) for the study tool.

To verify the validity of the differences, the arithmetic mean of the degrees of scientific outputs was extracted for each (teaching and teaching) separately as shown in Table No. (9)

Table (9) It shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of each (teaching - teaching) and the achieved T value

Comparison	Arithmetic averages	Standard Deviations	Calculated T-value	Tabular value	Degree of freedom	Indication level	Statistical significance
Lecturer Male	21,78	11,78	1,28	1,96	98	0,05	Nonfunctional
Lecture Female	18,93	10,02					

From the results shown in Table (9), we note that the arithmetic mean of the parameters' scores amounted to (21.78) and a standard deviation of (11.78), while the arithmetic mean of the parameters' scores amounted to (18.93), and a standard deviation of (10.02). The mean scores of the teachers are higher than the mean of the parameters, and for the purpose of ensuring that this difference reflects a true difference, two independent samples t-test was used. 98) At the level (0.05), and this means that the observed differences between the two mean are caused by chance factors, that is, they are not statistically significant.

The second hypothesis (there are no statistically significant differences in the average scores of master's holders and average doctoral degrees for the scientific outcomes tool in light of the data and impacts of the Covid 19 pandemic)

To validate the difference, the arithmetic mean of the degrees of scientific products for each of the master's degree holders on the one hand and the doctoral degree holders on the other hand was extracted separately as shown in Table No. (10)

Table (10) Shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations for both MSc and PhD degrees and the achieved t-value

Comparison	Arithmetic averages	Standard Deviations	Calculated T-value	Tabular value	Degree of freedom	Indication level	Statistical significance
Master	19,87	13,22	0,166	1,96	98	0,05	Nonfunctional
PhD	20,55	10,92					

It is clear from the results of Table No. (10) That the average score for master's holders was (19.87) and a standard deviation (13.22), while the average for PhD holders was (20,55) with a standard deviation. The deviation of (10.92) At first glance the mean score for PhD holders appears to be higher than that of MSc holders, and for the purpose of ensuring that this difference reflects a true difference, a t-test was used for two independent samples. and the degree of freedom (98) at the significance level (0.05), which means that the observed differences between the two mean are caused by chance factors, that is, they are not statistically significant.

The third hypothesis ((there are no statistically significant differences in the average scores of those infected with the Covid-19 epidemic and the average scores of non-infected people in the scientific results tool)

To verify this difference, the arithmetic averages of the degrees of scientific results for each of the professors infected with the pandemic and for those who did not have it were extracted separately as shown in Table (11)

Table (11) it shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations of both affected and uninjured professors, and the achieved t-value

Comparison	Arithmetic averages	Standard Deviations	Calculated T-value	Tabular value	Degree of freedom	Indication level	Statistical significance
Uninjured professors	17,82	10,24	3,02	1,96	98	0,05	Nonfunctional
Injured professors	12,82	1,91					

The arithmetic mean of the degrees of the professors not infected with the epidemic was used, and it was (17,82) and a standard deviation (10.24), while the arithmetic mean of the degrees of the infected professors was (12, 12). 82) and a standard deviation of (1.91). The grades of the non-infected professors are higher than the average grades of the professors affected by the epidemic, and for the purpose of ensuring that this difference reflects a real difference, the T-test was used for two independent samples, and it appeared that the calculated T value was (3,02) which is greater than the tabular value (1.96) And the degree of freedom that reached (98) at the significance level (0.05), which means that the observed differences are statistical. Great for the professors who were not affected by the epidemic at the expense of the professors infected with the epidemic, and this can be explained that the health and psychological impact they were exposed to is the professors infected with the epidemic. Pandemic during the period of infection. It had a significant impact on them, which negatively affected the levels of their scientific output.

The fourth hypothesis (there are no differences in the average degrees of scientific results according to the variable years of service)

To verify this difference, arithmetic means were extracted for each of the four groups. The mean scores for scientific results ranged from (7 to 21,19) and standard deviations ranged from (1.7 to 11,24) as shown in Table (12)

Table (12)It shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the research sample according to years of service

Years of service	average	standard deviation
5 years	7	1,7
10 years	19,40	6,81
20 years	22,92	12,15
20 and more	21,19	11,24

It appears from Table (12) that there is a discrepancy in the average degrees of scientific results according to the years of service, and for the purpose of ascertaining the observed differences reflect differences between the groups, a single metaphor analysis was used, as shown in Table (13)

Table (13)It shows the one-way analysis of variance to find the differences according to the variable years of service

Contrast Source	Mean Squares	Degree Of Freedom	Mean Squares	Q Value
Between Groups	15520,06	3	517,35	4,70
Within Groups	10546,93	96	109,86	
Total	12099	99		

It is clear from Table (13) that the calculated value (4.07) is greater than the tabular value (2.70) at the degrees of freedom (3-96) and the significance level (0.05), which indicates that there are differences. Between groups according to the variable years, and to ascertain the source of the difference, multiple comparisons were made (Schiff's test) as shown in Table (14)

Table (14)Displays multiple comparisons of average grades for years of service

Comparison	The difference between the two averages	Semantics (using SPSS)
5 and 10	4,58	Function
5 and 20	4.29	Function
5 and more than 20	4.38	Function
10 and 20	2.78	Nonfunctional
10 and more than 20	2.92	Nonfunctional
20 and more than 20	2,50	Nonfunctional

Table (14) shows that the noticeable difference was between the degree of service averages (5) years and the degrees of other averages, as they were less scientifically productive, which means that there is a significant effect of years of service for the scholar. The results instrument and the reason for this is the result of the scientific good that they have acquired in the writing of scientific research, authorship and other scientific activities.

*The fifth hypothesis (there are no differences in the average degrees of scientific products according to the changing scientific titles)

To verify this difference, the arithmetic averages of all the four groups were extracted, and the average degrees of scientific results ranged from (19.85 to 22,35) as shown in Table (15)

Table (15) It shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the research sample according to the scientific titles variable

Group	Averages	standard deviation
Assistant Lecturer	19,85	14,28
Lecturer	22,35	11,50
Assistant Prof.	20,04	10,88
Prof Dr.	20,44	10,84

It is clear from Table No. (15) that there is a discrepancy in the average degrees of scientific results according to the variable of academic titles, and for the purpose of ascertaining the noticeable differences that reflect the differences between groups, a single tabular analysis was used as shown in Table (16)

Table (16) Explains one-way analysis of variance to find differences according to the scientific titles variable

Contrast source	Mean squares	Degree of freedom	Mean squares	q value
between groups	60	3	20,04	0,16
within groups	12038,86	96	125,40	
total	12,99	99		

It seemed that the calculated value of (0.16) was less than the tabular value of (2.70) at the degrees of freedom (3-96) and the level of significance (0.05), which means that there are no differences. Between groups, and this can be explained that university professors were mastering their work through their practice of writing research papers and the accumulation of experiences, as well as their practice of all the activities assigned to them at the level of official assignment or volunteer work.

The sixth hypothesis (there are no differences in the average degrees of scientific results according to the different age groups of teachers)

To verify this difference, the arithmetic means were extracted for each of the four groups, where the average degrees of scientific results ranged from (12.07 to 21.92) as shown in Table (17)

Table (17) It shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the study sample according to the variable age of the college

average groups	Arithmetic	standard deviations
Thirties	12,07	6,91
Forties	21,92	11,39
fifties and beyond	21,78	10,55

It is clear from Table No. (17) That there is a discrepancy in the average degrees of scientific results according to the different age groups of faculty members, in order to ascertain the noticeable differences that reflect the differences between groups and one tab has been analyzed. Used as shown in Table No. (18)

Table (18) Explains one-way analysis of variance to find differences according to the variable age of the college

Contrast source	Mean squares	Degree of freedom	Mean squares	q value
between groups	1156,85	2	578,42	5,12
within groups	10942,14	97	112,80	
total	12099	99		

From Table (18) it appeared that the calculated value (5.12) is less than the tabular value (3.09) at the degree of freedom (2-97) and the level of significance (0.05), which means that there are differences between groups. To ascertain the source of the difference, multiple comparisons were made (Schiff's test) as shown in Table No. (19)

Table (19) Shows multiple comparisons of average scores for college age groups

Comparison	The difference between the two averages	Semantics (using SPSS)
Thirties with the forties and beyond	3,19	Function
Thirties, fifties and beyond	3,38	Function
forties with fifties	2,35	Nonfunctional

It is clear from Table No. (19) that the multiple comparisons that were made showed a noticeable difference between the degree of averages for the age groups of thirty and the degrees of other averages, as they were less productive from a scientific point of view compared to other ages, which means that there are differences in the groups for the ages of the forties, fifties and beyond, As indicated by the scientific output tool, and this can be explained as a result of the experience and practice gained by the owners of the age groups from the forties. The fifties and beyond, thus verifying the objectives and hypotheses of the study.

Conclusions

Urban health conditions and the repercussions of the spread of the Corona pandemic during the period from 2019 to 2022 led to many effects and variables that had repercussions on society and all state institutions, including undoubtedly higher education institutions, as they affected them. The level of scientific outputs, whether in the field of authorship, publishing, or internal and external scientific participation. The results of the statistics of this study have proven the validity of our findings, and for the purpose of brevity and accuracy of the conclusions, they can be classified into two directions, the first is negative and is determined by the following matters- :

First: The infection of many of the study community with the Corona epidemic prevented them from continuing to conduct advanced scientific research, as well as the decline in other scientific activities in most Iraqi universities, especially during the period 2019 to 2022.

Second: The lack of spending or the lack of spending in the field of scientific research and specialized literature was an additional reason for the infection of a number of university professors with the virus, which led to a decline in the level of academic scientific output.

Third: Undoubtedly, the circulation of news about the escalation of HIV infection rates among the study community, greatly affected the psychological state of other professors, and this was fully reflected on the level of their scientific giving, and a case witnessed. of regression as mentioned in the context of this study.

Fourth: The conditions of the health ban obligated the employment of e-learning that requires cognitive skills in information technology and knowledge technology, and it affected a number of professors who lack some of these skills, which was reflected in the interaction with many. Scientific activities based on distance education technologies have thus decreased their scientific products.

As for the positive effects, they can be identified through the following things:

First: The conditions of the ban and citizens' commitment to live in their homes allowed more time, especially for university professors, to devote themselves to researching the corridors of their personal libraries and working to complete their specialized research and studies. The tagged "education and community participation, the problem of absence and effectiveness of attendance" during the ban period, along with the author (Ramid, 2021) book "History of Contemporary Arab Countries."

Second: Activating workshops, seminars, symposia and specialized courses through electronic platforms, as it was another interface for the scientific activity of university professors from the professors of the study sample and the College of Education IbnRushd, and the participants obtained certificates of participation. Various certificates of appreciation.

Third: The continuation of holding electronic scientific conferences and discussing research through various electronic platforms provided the appropriate opportunity to participate in these conferences at the internal and external levels. Opportunities to subsequently evaluate, discuss and publish this research were positive to invest in the characteristics of distance education, after which the level of education was not affected. The scientific outputs of these professors, especially those who have experience in the field of e-learning technology.

Recommendations

First: The need for more guidance and direction for faculty members on the necessity of applying self- and societal prevention measures and the limits of their applications, and urging those who did not take the vaccine to receive doses to provide protection for themselves and others.

Second: To recommend that the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research direct universities to take care of research centers, especially those related to the production of knowledge needed by society, as well as establishing a system for development, creativity and scientific innovation. Limits of employing them in a technology that contributes to the productivity of knowledge, taking into account the capabilities of these centers to overcome problems the invisible.

Third: The recommendation of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research that it is necessary to activate the activities of cultural attaches abroad and urge them to pursue scientific activities and innovations in the country designated for them while trying to employ them in the country. Fields of scientific research and knowledge technology.

Fourth: The recommendation of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research to work on activating the full-time system for professors in Arab and international universities according to the twinning program.

Fifth: Recommending the necessity of re-evaluating and evaluating the scientific participation experience of professors through electronic platforms, especially in the matter of participation in scientific conferences in particular, and guidance on the development of electronic refereed journals that have the same characteristics and advantages as paper. Accredited and accredited scientific journals in scientific promotions.

Suggestions

- Working on the completion of other studies related to the consolidation of the scientific productive relationship with other variables such as (work satisfaction, the quality of the university professor's performance, and mental health)
- The study suggests conducting similar studies on educational and scientific topics whose results have declined due to the outbreak of the Corona pandemic, especially specialized educational, humanitarian and social topics.

References

- Shaheen, SherifKamel, 2013, The Arab League between the demands of Arab identity and the ambitions of global ranking, Academic Library, Cairo, Egypt.
- World Conference on Higher Education, 1998, Higher Education in the Twenty-first Century, Vision and Action, Working Document of the United Nations Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organization, Unesco, Paris.
- The Third Arab Report on Cultural Development, 2020, Global Research in Arab Universities, first edition, Arab Thought Foundation, Beirut, Lebanon.
- Al-Hadithi, Ibtisam, 2006, the scientific productivity of Saudi faculty members in the Colleges of Education for Girls in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, an evaluation study, studies in university education.
- Al-Rubaie, Saeed bin Hamad, 2008, Higher Education in the Age of Changes, Challenges, and Future Prospects, first edition, Dar Al-Shorouk for Publishing and Distribution.
- Rumid, Sabah Mahdi, 2021, History of the Contemporary Arab Countries, Dar Adnan for Publishing and Distribution, Baghdad.
- Ramid, Sabah Mahdi, Jamil, Muhammad Amer, 2021, Education and Community Participation, The Problematic of Absence and Effectiveness of Attendance, Adnan Publishing and Distribution House, Baghdad.
- Hamami, Youssef, and Khalaf Al-Tal, 1994, Measuring Productivity in Service Organizations Using Electronic Matrices, Yarmouk Research Journal, Human and Social Sciences Series, Volume 21, Issue 2, issued by the Deanship of Scientific Research and Graduate Studies, Yarmouk University, Jordan.
- Al-Tal, Saeed, 1997, University Teaching Rules, Dar Al-Fikr for Printing, Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
- Andrea, 1994, What does it mean to be educated in 2020? Translated by Atef Interview, University of Berkeley.
- Al-Shaya, Muhannad, 2006, The reality of the scientific production of faculty members and its obstacles in the faculties of human sciences at King Saud University, College of Education Research Center, Deanship of Scientific Research, King Saud University.
- Al-Nima, Taha, Al-Ajili, Sabah (2004) Introduction to Psychology, issued by the Scientific Academy, Department of Human Sciences, Introduction to Human Sciences series, Scientific Academy Press, Baghdad.
- Hallak.j.,1996,The analysis of Educational costs and expenditure, Paris, Unesco: Internationallnstitute for Education planning.
- Robbins Stephen.1990, Organization Theory: Structure,Design and Applications-3 R D Englewood Clifls, Nj:Printice-Hall INC.
- Deming W. Edward, 1999, Special Reports Managing productivity Bavendam Research. INC. Mereer Island. Vo14.

Schafer, William D. (2002) Education Applied Assessment professionals at the master Level p.1.8.U.S.A; Maryland

Alken, L.R (1988). Psychological Testing and Assessment, Bostom, Allyn& Bacon

Ebel, R.L. (1972) Essentials of Education Measurement, NewjersyEnglwood Cliffs Frrentice-Hill.

Author Information

Assistant Professor Dr. Muhammad Amer Jamil

Baghdad Directorate of Education Rusafa First, Iraq
College of Education IbnRushd, University of
Baghdad, Iraq

Prof. Dr. Sabah Mahdi Rumayd

Baghdad Directorate of Education Rusafa First, Iraq
College of Education IbnRushd, University of
Baghdad, Iraq
